

THE IMPACT OF LEADERSHIP STYLE TO THE TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract:

Leadership style, transformational leadership has a positive impact on teachers' job satisfaction. The principal leads by organising all work at school. Satisfaction from work is determined by internal and external factors. Leadership, the behaviour that allows principals to create positive school cultures and increase teachers' job satisfaction has often been the subject of much study. This review focuses on some of the theory and recent studies that are related to the impact of leadership style and transformational leadership style in the teachers' job satisfaction. Some findings of the study were: (a) satisfaction from work is determined by internal factors, and external factors that have an impact on the job dissatisfaction; (b) these factors are in different ways determinants of job satisfaction; (c) leadership style plays an important role and is connected with the teachers' job satisfaction; (d) dimensions as charisma, individualised consideration, intellectual stimulation and influence have a positive impact on job satisfaction of the teachers.

Keywords: leadership, leadership style, teachers' job satisfaction, transformational leadership

1. Introduction

Effectiveness of school depends on the efficiency of management ability, personality, and interaction with stakeholders (Hallinger and Heck, 1998). The role of the principal has become more complex, from the principal as an instructional leader to the role of transformational leader. The duties of principals extend beyond that of instructional leaders to one that is administrative and managerial (Fullan, 1991). Principals' relationship with teachers affects the attitude of teachers to the school and determines

the climate of relations. Successful leaders focus on the relationship and the motivation of the people than in the establishment and maintenance of the system. *"Capacity building is the core route to improvement"* (Fullan, 2008:54).

A satisfied teacher cares for the students' welfare. Teacher's job satisfaction is seen as a key factor in the school's dynamics and is considered as the primary dependent variable in terms of the effectiveness of school. Safe environment of the school leadership, collaboration with colleagues, high involvement of parents, learning resources can play a role in effectiveness, increase engagement in school and promote job satisfaction (Darling – Hammond, 2003). It is important to gather and understand the satisfaction and dissatisfaction of the teachers' job as an indicator to strengthen the education system.

2. Leadership

Contemporary literature and studies bring multiple definitions for leadership. *"Leadership is not mobilising others to solve the problem, because they know how to solve, but they help them cope with the problem, which is not successfully resolved"* (Fullan, 2004:1).

Leadership is a relationship *"between leaders and followers impactful targeting the real changes and outcomes that reflect their common goal"* (Daft, 2005:5). Burns called *"...leadership as one of the most studied phenomena and less accessible to the earth"* (Burns, 1978:2). Leadership is often regarded as a critical point of success or failure of the organisation (Bass, 1990). Burke (2008) defines leadership as vision, change, its influence, intuition, and persuasive skills presentative reward people for doing the work and providing opportunities to learn new skills. Hoy & Miskel (2001) define leadership as the art of transformation people and organisation in order to improve the organisation. In this regard, it sets the task manager, explains, oversees activities teachers develop a relationship between themselves and teachers, so they motivate, inspire to promote productivity among teachers. Yulk defines leadership as a process that carries a person or group over others for structured activities and relationships in the group or organisation (cited by Bush, 2013).

2.1 School leadership is specific

Fullan (2001) calls school leadership complex. He lists four ways in which school leadership is complex: engagement

- the changes we are seeking are deeper than at the first thought;
- as such, there are a number of dilemmas in deciding what to do;
- one needs to act differently in different situations or phases of the change process; and

- advice comes in the form of guidelines for action, not steps to be followed (Fullan, 2001).

Leadership practice has the potential to empower teachers towards a commitment to change and enhance their learning in school organisation (Bogler, 2001; Fullan, 2002; Day et al., 2001). Leithwood (2006) makes a simple definition of leadership calling leadership and influence. According to his goal of stability is called "*management*" and that is the goal of improving management have a synergy relationship that plays a significant role in the success of the school. Goleman et al., (2002) argue that the modern principals will be able to think conceptually as they transform the organisation through people and teams and will also need to possess strong interpersonal skills, be able to get along with others, and exercise high levels of intelligence and energy (cited by Marshall, 2004)

As an important component of management principal has two of the important responsibilities, manages and controls the involvement of teachers in the teaching process and learning. Everything in the school is organised by principal. The efficiency depends on the efficiency of school management; ability, personality, interaction with stakeholders (Bush 2011; Hallinger and Heck, 1998). For Bryk principal is one of the factors that makes the difference between changing in success and changing in failure (cited by Fullan, 2001).

Leadership plays a key role in the effectiveness of change in education.

2.2 Leadership theory, leadership style

There are many adjectives that characterise leadership style, which often lead to confusion in determining the appropriate qualities. (Leithwood, K., Louis, SK, Anderson, S, Ehlstrom, K. 2004.)

Great "Man", Trait Theory (1900's-1930's): this theory is based on the belief that leader is an extraordinary man with innate qualities to lead. *Behavioural Style Theory* (1940's-1950's): this theory focuses on behaviour rather than on leaders' quality. *Situational Leadership*: This approach based on specific situation. *Contingency Theory*: according to this theory it is the concentration on the random situations. *Transactional Theory*: This approach emphasises the relationship of leaders to followers, focus on the mutual benefits of a "*contract*" through which gives the driver a reward in exchange for engagement gratitude and loyalty of employees. *Transformational Theory*: The key concept here is the role of leaders in the provision and implementation of the transformation of the organisation's performance

Blanchard and Hersey (1996) constructed the theory of leadership styles based on two basic concepts: the style of leadership and organisation, providing staff support. They emphasise the effective use of style depending on the situation and the maturity

of the staff. They listed four leadership styles: autocratic, consultative, collaborative, democratic. Blake and Mouton (1994) listed five leadership styles in two dimensions: people versus task orientation. They stressed that the best style for the effectiveness of the organisation is, when the headmaster possesses them both, high orientation tasks (score), and relationship (cited by Everard et al., 2004).

2.3 Contingency theory

Tannenbaum and Schmidt (1958) present a scheme of leadership styles and form orientations: orientation toward results and orientation toward relations. The theory of Tannenbaum and Schmidt suggested the idea that leadership behaviour varies along a continuum and that as one moves away from the autocratic extreme the amount of subordinate participation and involvement in decision taking increases. They also suggested that the kind of leadership represented by the democratic extreme of the continuum will be rarely encountered in formal organisations.

They identified some leadership style:

- autocratic: leader shows what work to do and does not expect questions from them.
- cogent: the leader takes decisions without asking but believes that people will be motivated if they believe that decisions are good.
- consulting: in this style the leader considers teachers' words. Teachers believe that they influence in decision making.
- democratic: in this style the Principal allows teachers to make decisions, he is the observer. So he lets them make decisions instead to be compelling.

This theory or approach differs from previous theories. Style approach may be appropriate in different situations. The more a person is concerned about the results, the less he or she would be concerned about the relationship and vice versa (cited by Everard et al., 2004).

According to Hallinger (2003) leadership should be seen as a mutual process and not just a way to influence one over the others. Effective principal responds to context and behaviour takes the form of school context.

Hallinger proposes three sets of leadership dimensions in his model:

- defining the school's mission, includes framing and then communicating the school's goals;
- managing the instructional program, includes supervising and evaluating teaching, coordinating the curriculum, and monitoring student progress;

- promoting a positive school learning climate: encompasses protecting teaching time, promoting professional development, maintaining high visibility, providing incentives for teachers, and providing incentives for learning (cited by Leithwood et al., 2006:20).

According to Goleman the principal must use some leadership styles depending on the situation (cited by Fullan 2001, 2004). He defined emotional intelligence as a leader's ability to manage himself and his relationship relative to the four emotional capabilities of self-awareness, self-management, social-awareness, and social skill. In his theory, he combined the five elements of emotional intelligence and listed six leadership styles:

- Authoritarian: the leader mobilises people toward a vision — "*Come with me*".
- Affiliative: the leader creates harmony and builds emotional bonds — "*People come first*".
- Coaching: the leader develops people for the future — "*Try this*".
- Democratic: the leader forges consensus through participation — "*How do you?*".
- Coercive: the leader demands compliance. — "*Do what I tell you*".

He recommends that leaders use as many of the six leadership styles as possible to create a state of "*fluid leadership*". "*Transactional, transformational leadership type*" (Burns, Bass, Leithwood, Fullan).

Burns (1978) described followers and there nor inspiring each other leaders to achieve "*higher levels of morality and motivation such as justice and equality*" (p.20). He conceived of as a transformational leader; bringer of change, solving situations, motivational potential reach of followers, satisfy higher needs, recognise competition and conflict. Burns claims that real leadership not only creates change and achieves goals within the environment, but changing people involved in the actions necessary but even better: both followers and leaders are ennobled. A transactional leadership has to do with everyday practices; labour management, tasks, skills and individual opportunities, individual needs and values, which affect transactional daily.

Bass (1985) based on empirical data of Burns built his work to ascertain the validity of transformational leadership and interactive. He studied transformational leadership type including social change. Bass transformational leadership conceived of the four components:

- the *charismatic leader* or idealised influence includes leaders who are admired, trusted, respected by subordinates, take risks and look for moral and ethical standards, act as a model for their subordinates;

- inspirational motivation challenge appears when the leader generates, displays strong commitment to the objectives, has high expectations and cultivate the spirit of team work to subordinates;
- intellectual stimulation occurs when subordinates publicly criticised not encouraged to be creative, to discuss assumptions, to solve the problem, to change the old methods and cope with new solutions;
- includes individual considerations as mentor leader who cares for the needs of subordinates and recognise individual differences. His model includes three interactive dimensions of transactional leadership.

Leader urges collective vision and motivation of staff members to achieve an excellent performance (Bass, 1985). Transactional leadership emphasises the relationship of leaders with followers, focuses on the mutual benefits of a "contract", through which a leader provides rewards in recognition of the commitment and loyalty of employees. According to Avolio & Bass, good leaders use more transformational leadership than transactional, but used together are effective (cited by Lewis et. al., 2011). After 1980, the focus was on *transactional* leadership and after 90s, the attention of researchers focused on a transformational leadership. In this new conceptual structure, management is not focused on the curriculum, but in building the capacity of the organisation, to set goals and to support subsistence-changing technological core (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2006).

Based on transformational leadership Leithwood & Janzi developed a model, which included some of the characteristics of transformational leadership. According to them leader who had success was that he had used a number of *mechanisms in management, staff motivation and involvement in the school climate change*. They included four dimensions in their model:

- setting directions. includes building school vision, developing specific goals and priorities and holding high expectations;
- developing people refers to providing intellectual stimulation, offering individualised support and modelling desirable professional practices and values;
- redesigning the organisation includes developing a collaborative school culture, creating structures to foster participation in school decisions and creating productive community relationships;
- managing the instructional programme refers to the establishment of stable routines, structures and procedures to support change.

Leithwood defined setting the basic guidelines as a key component of leadership that mobilises employees organises, provides a purpose and vision. Although this component plays a major role in motivating people about work are not the only ones

who do this (Leithwood, 2004:12). Developing people is a dimension that provides intellectual stimulation, individual support. Re-dimensioning organisation provides collaboration within and outside the school. Based on empirical studies they proved the validity and effect of transformational leadership on climate change.

Fullan (2001a) identified the following five traits that principals must develop:

- a strong sense of moral purpose,
- an understanding of the dynamics of change,
- a commitment to developing and sharing new knowledge,
- a capacity for coherence making and
- emotional intelligence as they build and foster relationships. "*The effective change leader actively participates as a learner in helping the organisation improves*" (Fullan, 2011:5).

Being absorbed by decades of experience in international education reform Fullan has highlighted six secrets of change:

- *The first secret: love your employees.* It means to help all them find meaning, develop skills, and direct personal pleasure, contributing to simultaneously fulfil their goals and those of the organisation.

- *The second secret: teachers aim Merge.* The concentration of faculty with solid objectives and tight performance makes passive and hostile employees. Leaders create the conditions for effective interaction and intervene only when necessary, otherwise should allow the group to find its own equilibrium. According to Fullan the interaction between faculty members is more than just cooperation; it is social and intellectual conception of an organisation.

- *Third secret: capacity building is predominant.* Problems solve when people believe that they will be not punished if they assume the risk. Intimidation is not the best way to motivate people. Capacity building brings people with talent and helps develop individually and collectively.

- *Fourth secret: learning is work.* Teaching staff must carry out the main task and learn to improve what it does. Learning during working every day, it is work.

- *Fifth secret: transparency rules.* The transparency rules are the basis of success and appear as a necessity (Fullan 2008). Effective organisations embrace transparency. People cover problems if the environment will punish them. Culture should be developed where the problems appear to have normal solution.

- *Six secret: learning system.* Organisations fail to maintenance of continuous learning because concentrate on individual directors. Progressive

leaders put the organisation in episodic commitments with ups and downs (Fullan, 2010).

Personality traits and behaviour associated with the contextual situation and opportunity, vision, cooperation and broad-based decision making make leadership a unique process.

3. Job satisfaction

Satisfaction at work can be conceived as a multi-dimensional concept that includes a set of satisfying and dissatisfying feelings in which employees perceive their work. Although there is no definitive definition of the job satisfaction, Hoppock (1935) based on his study; found that job satisfaction is a combination of psychological circumstances, physiological environment that cause a person to say, *"I am pleased with my job."*

The employee satisfaction at work has been the centre of attention especially in these years and the organisation cannot be quality competitive if human resources are not satisfied and achievement quality of the organisation is first connected to the employee satisfaction at work (Garcia – Bernal, et. al., 2005).

Mumford (1983) has defined job satisfaction as a better adaptation between what employees want to achieve in their work, labour needs, expectations and aspirations and what is required to do their work, organisation working. In his statement, both workers and employers can be satisfied in a form of equilibrium if the needs ensure a good fit. Satisfaction at work is defined as an attitude, but that affects feelings, actions and behaviours. Locke (1976) has defined it as *"... as a satisfactory or positive emotional state resulting from the evaluation of one's work or work experience"* (Locke, 1976:1304). Various factors affect differently on various individual. In several studies conducted in our country, it is shown that despite the difficult working conditions (external factors); teachers were satisfied with their job.

3.1 Job satisfaction factors

Studies, which are based on several theories about the factors that affect teacher's job satisfaction, turn out to have different attitudes of teachers towards influencing factors. Safe environment of the school leadership, collaboration with colleagues, high involvement of parents, learning resources can play a role in effectiveness, increase engagement in school and promote job satisfaction (Darling – Hammond, 2003).

Theories of Herzberg (1953) known as the *"Two Factor Theory"* has delineated the internal factors (motivators) that influence job satisfaction, and external factors (hygiene factors) that influence job dissatisfaction. According to him, the factors that cause

pleasure or motivation are: work, achievement, recognition, responsibility. Factors that cause dissatisfaction or hygiene factors are: cooperation with colleagues, working conditions, director, salary, etc. Researchers, based on the Maslow's theory of a Need, believe that this theory is a foundation to establish the satisfaction of teachers ranging from basic human needs (lower level) to a greater degree.

Moslow, Herzberg, Likert have seen the development of motivation as the main factor of job satisfaction, but it depends on the individual and on the circumstances (cited from Mumford 1978). Herzberg (1968) asserted that the way to motivate the employee is to enrich their work. He points out that they will perform better and will make more if they have challenges and will be psychologically satisfied by their work. But not all employees like challenges (Lazenby, 2008). Some challenges can bring pleasure at work for some, and disappointment for others. For Mumford (1978) the needs are associated with the job satisfaction not only in Moslow vertical hierarchy (from lowest to highest), but also in lateral terms. As long as the level of the individual needs is associated with the pleasure, he will be satisfied and the results will be positive. Maslow emphasises that the work performance is likely not to depend on the adjustment between individual's needs and work, but on what he should do about connected with individual needs and what it is likely to do.

Satisfaction from work is determined by internal factors, and external factors that have an impact on the job dissatisfaction. Literature and theory offers us examples where these factors are in different ways determinants of job satisfaction.

4. Transformational leadership and teachers' job satisfaction in several studies

Leaders who share information with teacher and include them in managerial decision positively affects their commitment to working class and teachers are more satisfied (Bogler, 2001). Lashbrook (1997) stated that the leadership style plays an important role in job satisfaction (cited by Voon et al., 2010). Bogler, Heller, McKeen found that different leadership style brings up different working atmosphere and directly impacts job satisfaction (cited by Voon et al., 2010).

Blake and Mouton have seen the principal and his style as a determinant in job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has other perspectives that influence rewards and efforts as important. (Cited by Mumford 1978.) In a case study on job satisfaction and its connection with leadership style and decision-making resulted that school principal decision plays the role of a mediator between teachers' job satisfaction and leadership style (Hui et., al, 2013). Hariri (2011) study results show that job satisfaction was not high and the relationship between managing style and job satisfaction has been very meaningful. Using leadership style in the right way has impacted the jobs satisfaction,

commitment and productivity. Transformational leadership directly impacts employee job satisfaction (Voon et al., 2011).

The findings of Harris and Lowery (2002) show that the principals, who respects and treats every member of the school community in a fair and equal, displays behaviour that encourages and create a positive school climate. Martin (2009) in the result of his study indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between most of the factors of the leadership styles of principals and the factors of school culture. Findings indicated that a positive relationship existed between all of the factors of transformational leadership and all of the factors of school culture. Principals' collegiality with teachers, according Rosenholtz, is effective and affects school performance, when goals and objectives achievement go into teaching function (cited by Elmore, 2000). The study of Commonwealth Secretariat (1996) asserts that "the head plays an important role in the effectiveness of the organisation" (cited by Bush & Middlewood, 2013:9).

Griffin & Moorhed point that school climate can be manipulated and direct impact on people's behaviour associated with school (cited by Harris 2002) .They point out that creating a positive school climate are essential:

- job satisfaction;
- human dignity.

According to Gill (2006), a transformer leader is positively correlated with performance in business, military, education, government and non-profit organisations (cited by Lewis et.al). Judge & Polis (2004) in their study found that transformational leadership and reward contingent have a significant outcome, which includes employee satisfaction and organisational performance; Tucker & Russel (2004) concluded that transformational leadership has some influence in the culture of the organisation and transform it (cited by Lewis, 2011).

A transformational leadership makes the leader in certain moments; when there are problems require a top-down approach, to establish clear learning goals and achievements towards their leadership (Fullan, 2002). Results from the Pearson Correlation indicated that all five transformational leadership style dimensions and one transactional leadership dimension derived from the MLQ were statistically significant at the .0001 level and showed positive, moderate correlations with teacher job satisfaction (Biggerstaf, 2012). Emery (2007) in their study shows that: leadership behaviour and teachers outcome significantly were correlated; dimensions of transformational leadership, charisma, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration have a strong correlation with job satisfaction and commitment. Lowe, Kroeck, & Sivasubramaniam (1996) found from a meta-analysis of results from 39 studies that three transformational leadership behaviours (charisma, individualised

consideration, intellectual stimulation) are related to leadership effectiveness in most studies (cited by Leithwood et. al 2006). The transformational leadership behaviours correlated more strongly with leadership effectiveness than did the transactional leadership behaviours. Findings in the Horn-Turpin (2009) indicated that significant relationships existed at the $p < .01$ level between the variables of administrative support, organisational commitment, and job satisfaction.

Day's et al. (2001) by research in 12 schools 'effective' in England and Wales concludes that good leaders are informed and transmit clear personal values and education that reflect their moral goals for the school (citar nag Bush 2008). Results of a study in Albania high school show that leadership styles affect the climate of the school. Collaborative and authoritarian style influence on school climate and the impact is a high degree of statistical confidence ($p = 0:01$). Authoritarian style harms and hinders open school climate ($r = -.581, p < 0:01$). Collaborative style improves and encourages open school climate and strengthen the perception of teachers, that the institution is open and cooperative ($r = .597, p < 0:01$) (Rapti, 2013). According to a study in Albania basic education teachers resulted in moderate positive correlations between leadership style, relationships with colleagues and job satisfaction ($r = .337, p < 0:01; r = .341, p < 0:01$) (Bezati, 2012).

Based on the empirical studies above results that transformational leadership dimensions affects job satisfaction of teachers.

7. Conclusion

Literature review reveals an evolution of management theories of human theory of "great" in the theory of transformation. Early theories tend to focus on the characteristics and behaviours of successful leaders, while subsequent theories begin to consider the role of followers and contextual nature of leadership. This brings up a positive climate and increased job satisfaction of teachers. Satisfaction from work is determined by internal factors, and external factors that have an impact on the job dissatisfaction. These factors are in different ways determinants of job satisfaction. Leadership style plays an important role and is connected with the teachers' job satisfaction. Dimensions as charisma, individualised consideration, intellectual stimulation and influence have a positive impact on job satisfaction of the teachers.

There are several gaps in our knowledge about school leadership and leadership style. There are some questions for further studies. The school leadership is specific; is there enough support in legislation the use of different styles? Has responsibility the principal to its functions in the quality of staff? Are there differences in the assessment of principal based on several difficulties; quality of school, schools in the suburbs or in

rural areas? Who bears responsibility for some external factors that influence the teachers job dissatisfaction are not at the right level?

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